
The Contrast Between Flora Nwapa's and Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka's Women of the Lake

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ABSTRACT

Through this study, the purpose has been to reveal the contrast between Flora Nwapa's and Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka's women of lake by focusing on each authoress's work namely Flora Nwapa's Efurú and Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka's Mammywater Tales. To begin, the scrutiny has been to discover how each writer's deity selects her worshippers. And then to shed light on whether or not each scholar's woman of the lake tells her prospective disciples the benefits and drawbacks of the pact.

At the end, it has been found out that Flora Nwapa's deity does not choose her disciples physically but the latter realizes it through facts in her life such as : wealth, barrenness, and dreams. Unlike Flora Nwapa's, Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka's contacts her future worshippers physically before becoming her disciples. When it comes to unveil if each deity informs her future devotees about the benefits and drawbacks of their relationship, Flora Nwapa's woman of the lake does not tell her prospective disciples what they will gain and lose. However, Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka informs her future worshippers about the advantages and disadvantages of their relationship.

KEYWORDS : Woman of the lake, deity, Uhammiri, worshipper

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I-INTRODUCTION

All over the world, people's identities are defined by several facts such as beliefs, customs, social behaviours and so forth. Thus, in Africa, people tend to believe in supernatural beings that form the grassroots of their life. In Nigeria, people, from Igbo tribe, believe in a supernatural being called the woman of the lake. For Igbo people, the woman of the lake also known as Uhammiri in Igbo society or Mammywater is the cornerstone of their life either during good times or bad ones. As a result, the interplay between Mammywater and Igbo people has been depicted in their literature by several authors mainly Flora Nwapa and her niece Njideka Ibuaka. While reading the works of the authoresses mentioned above, one is tempted to discover whether these writers have the same grasp of this supernatural being as they are both from the same tribe as well as the same family. Consequently, through this work, the main concern is to delve into each writer's work to reveal whether or not Flora Nwapa and Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka have an identical view of Mammywater. To carry out the work, the focus is based on answering two questions : first, how does each authoress's woman of the lake select her worshippers ? And then second, does each authoress's deity inform her prospective worshippers about the advantages and disadvantages of being in relationship with her ?

Before heading to the completion of this study, it is worthy tackling its literature review to show what other scholars have discovered about the woman of the lake and the scientific contribution of this research to the human kind.

In his article entitled Uhammiri Deity and Women : a Study of Flora Nwapa's Efurú and Idu, Razinat Mohammed depicts the swap that exists between the woman of the lake and her worshippers. In fact, through the study, its author describes the fact Uhammiri provides her worshippers with wealth and in return she denies them fertility. This denial of fertility is not well appreciated by the Igbo society. Consequently, Igbo people show their predilection for children to the detriment of wealth because wealth is not worthier than children.

Like Mohammed, Davies Ufuoma has researched on the Lake Goddess as well. In fact, in his work : the Goddess Alternative Realities, Transformation and the Goddess Myth in African Women's Fiction: A Sociological Perspective of Flora Nwapa's Efurú, Davies Ufuoma argues that, in Efurú, Flora Nwapa is repainting the true image of the woman who was badly represented by her

male counterparts. As a result, in depicting the Lake Goddess as an entity that provides her worshippers with wealth as well as children, Flora Nwapa is shedding light on the woman's gender values in the society.

In this article entitled : Flora Nwapa and Uhammiri/Ogbuide, the Lake Goddess : An Evolving Relationship, its authoress Sabine Jell-Bahlsen, quoted in *Emerging Perspectives on Flora Nwapa : Critical and Theoretical Essays* edited by Marie Umeh, paints Flora Nwapa's ambivalence about the Lake Goddess. As a matter of fact, at the beginning of her fiction mainly in her first novels : *Efuru* and *Idu*, Flora Nwapa has painted the Lake Goddess as an entity that denies her worshippers fertility and in return provides them with wealth. This view related to Uhammiri changes over time in her fiction. In later works such as *Never Again*, the Lake Goddess, Uhammiri is depicted as the provider of fertility, protector of Ugwuta people during the Biafra War and healer in her last opus entitled 'The Lake Goddess'.

Bringing her contribution in the study related to the woman of the lake, Eleonara Chiavetta has what follows to say in her article : *The Igbo Religious World in Flora Nwapa's Fiction*. Through her contribution, Chiavetta portrays the interplay between Igbo people and their religious beliefs. To carry out her research, she sheds light on the place of Uhammiri among Igbos as : the provider of fertility and she enables women to achieve economic independence. Besides what is mentioned above, the woman of the lake is a source of moral manners. As a result, anybody, who cannot comply with her rules, is doomed to face a misfortune.

Like the scholars above, Dr. Seema Malpotra has carried out the research on Uhammiri as well. In fact, in his work : *The Mythic World in the Fiction of Flora Nwapa*, Dr. Malpotra posits that in depicting the woman of the lake in her fiction, Nwapa features the magnitude of power the woman has over Ugwuta people. Thus, In painting the woman of the lake as provider of fertility, wealth, and protection, Nwapa gives credit to women.

The completion of this investigation will be done through the reader-response approach. In this approach, 'the argument goes something like this : a text does not even exist , in a sense, until it is read by some reader. Indeed, the reader has a part in creating or actually does create the text. It is somewhat like the old question posed in philosophy classes , if a tree falls in the forest and no one hears it, does not it make sound ? Reader-response critics are saying that in effect, if a text does not have a reader, it does not exist...(H,c,A L :80)'

As for the structure of this study, it has been framed into two main parts which are divided into two subtitles each : the first part is entitled the selection of worshippers which has two subtitles namely Flora Nwapa's woman of the lake's selection of disciples and Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka's woman of the lake's selection of disciples . The second is the aftermath of signing a pact with the woman of the lake which has two subtitles as well : the aftermath of signing a pact with Flora Nwapa's woman of the lake and the aftermath of signing a pact with Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka's woman of the lake.

II- THE SELECTION OF WORSHIPPERS

A worshipper of a deity is anybody who serves the latter for any given purpose. The relationship between a deity and its devotee might be in order to gain a favour in which in return can be riches, fertility and so forth. Thus, in this section, the main objective is to get into the depth of each authoress's work that is *Efuru* by Flora Nwapa and *Mammywater Tales* by Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka to pinpoint how each woman of the lake selects her worshippers.

2.1-Flora Nwapa's Woman of Lake's Selection of Disciples

In Flora Nwapa's first novel *Efuru*, eponymous character had difficulties in conceiving although she was living in a couple with a man called Adizua. As in Africa, children are everybody's wish, when *Efuru* and Adizua lived in the house but the former could not conceive , people could not help gossiping because of *Efuru*'s incapacity to give birth as follows :

Neighbours talked as they were bound to talk. They did not see the reason why Adizua should not marry another woman since, according to them, two men do not live together. To them *Efuru* was a man she could not reproduce(1966:24).

Through this passage Flora Nwapa asks people not to talk about other people's business before being beware of what they are going through. In this extract, *Efuru*'s neighbours gossiped for the mere sake of talking. Nobody could wonder why *Efuru* could not give birth albeit she was living with a man. According to *Efuru*'s neighbours, she was a freak. Consequently, although *Efuru* appeared to be a woman, her incapacity to conceive makes people argue that she is a man because if she were a real woman, *Efuru* would give birth. Thus, for fear of being an outcast because children are the prerequisite of any peaceful marriage in her society, *Efuru* went to her father. As soon as she told her father what she was going through, the latter reacted in the following terms :'Something must be done, my daughter, it is not in our blood. Our women are productive. There must be a reason for this. We shall see a dibia(1966 : 24)'.*Efuru*'s father's reaction conveys the existence of something unusual in *Efuru*'s life. As Nwashike Ogene, *Efuru*'s father, knew the history of his family, *Efuru*'s barrenness was something strange to their Family. Consequently, *Efuru*'s father mentioned the consultation of a dibia. A dibia is an oracle in Ugwuta. He sees what humans cannot see with their natural eyes. A dibia an intermediary between the physical world and the supernatural one. As a result, he can solve any problems caused by supernatural forces. Thus, according to *Efuru*'s father, his daughter's condition could be supernatural and a dibia was the only one who could find a solution to it.

When a dibia was consulted, after the divination, he requested what follows to be done :

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"...Nwashike, this is what your daughter will do every Afo day. She is to sacrifice to the ancestors. It is much, but she will have to do it regularly. Every Afo day, she is to buy uziza, alligator pepper, and kola from the market. Uziza must be bought every Nkwo day from a pregnant woman. Every Afo day before the sun goes down or when the sun is here," and he pointed to the direction, "she should put these things in a small calabash and go down to the lake; there she will leave the calash to float away. So go home young woman and be cheerful. Next year during the Owu festival if nothing happens to you, come back to me. Go in peace(1966: 26)."

When the dibia asked that Efuru had to sacrifice and the items requested were : Uziza, alligator pepper, and kola which were to be put in a small calabash and left floating away at the lake, this passage was a hint of a relationship between Efuru and a Lake deity. Consequently, as what the dibia requested was performed accordingly, Efuru's mother-in-law and Ajanupu had a conversation in following terms :

"Has your daughter told you anything? Ajanupu asked her sister the following morning.

"No, she hasn't. What happened?

"She hasn't mentioned anything to you about her health?

"No, she has not. Is anything wrong?

"She does not know then. And you, haven't noticed anything yourself?

"No, I have not."

"You are just a woman for nothing. You can't see, you can even hear smell. Your daughter-in-law is pregnant."

"Efuru is pregnant? Orisha, thank you.' She raised her two hands to the sky, then knelt down and bowed her head, knocking it to the floor of the room, thanking Orisha, who is God(1966:27)..."

The passage above is nearly a confirmation of a relationship between Efuru and a lake deity. As a matter of fact, after performing a sacrifice requested by the dibia at the lake, Efuru who had been incapable of conceiving was made pregnant. As a result, Efuru gave a birth to a daughter called Ogonim who unfortunately died while her father Adizua was on a trip in Ndony, a village in the vicinity of Ugwuta. Since Adizua never came back home from Ndony either when his daughter died or during the period following their daughter's death, Efuru left Adizua's place for her father's house. While she was living at her father's place, Efuru remarried this time a man called Gilbert Eneberi. Unfortunately at this man's place, there was recurrence of Efuru's barrenness. Besides her difficulties to conceive, Efuru had strange dreams about the woman of the lake. As a father is nearly his child's God on earth, Efuru went to explain her dreams to her father who reacted as follows :

"Dreams? What kind of dreams?" Efuru's father asked, very interested.

"I dream several nights of the lake and the woman of the lake. Two nights ago, the dream was very vivid. I was swimming in the lake, when a fish raised its head and asked me to follow it. Foolishly I swam out to follow it. It dived and I dived too. I got to the bottom of the lake and to my surprise, I saw an elegant woman, very beautiful, combing her long black hair with a golden comb. When she saw me, she stopped combing her hair and smiled at me and asked me to come in(1966:146).

The fact that Efuru sees the woman of the lake in her dreams is a fool proof of the relationship between the woman of the lake and Efuru. Consequently, one can argue that Efuru has been chosen by the woman of the lake as her worshipper. As a matter of fact, when Efuru finished explaining her dreams to her father, the latter answered in the following way :

"Your dream is good. The woman of the lake, our Uhammiri has chosen you to be one of her worshippers. You have to see a dibia first and he will tell you what to do."

"Chosen me to be one of her worshippers!" "Yes, my daughter."

"Why?" "I don't know, my daughter, your mother had similar dreams."

"When can we see the dibia then? "We shall go on Afo day." (1966: 147)"

The reaction of Efuru's father confirms the existence of a relationship between Efuru and the woman of the lake. As a result, Efuru's plight is due to her relationship with Uhammiri that she never knew. The difficulties to conceive Efuru faces have been caused by the relationship she has with the woman of the lake.

In conclusion, after the scrutiny related to Flora Nwapa's woman of the lake's choice of worshippers, it is worthy positing that Flora Nwapa's woman of the lake chooses her disciples without any prior consultation. Whenever Uhammiri chooses the woman who should worship her, she does it while the prospective worshipper is unaware of the pact. Thus, the disciple will realize their relationship by witnessing difficulties to conceive and having dreams with the deity. After discovering the way Flora Nwapa's woman of the lake selects her adorers, in the following section, the focus will be on how Ndjideka Nwapa- Ibuaka's woman of the lake chooses her devotees.

2.3- Ndjideka Nwapa- Ibuaka's Woman of the Lake's Selection of Disciples

In Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka's Mammywater Tales, her woman of the lake does shapeshifting. As a result, the deity can either be invisible or visible in the flesh to her prospective devotees. As a matter of fact, the woman of lake came to the market in person as a beautiful lady on Nkwo day, where she met Mr. Agwo to whom she assigned a mission after taking him to her realm under the lake as follows :

'Tomorrow is Nkwo day in people's land. I want you to bring me feedback about my worshippers.' Agwo said, 'Is that all?' Mammywater said that it was.

She continued: 'You must go to the market and look for Mrs. Egbenuka and her friend. They are supposed to go to Ogbuide Lake dressed in red and white clothing and perform special sacrifices... Your job is to follow them to the lake and make sure that they are performing the rituals. If not, you must come back and tell me immediately (M. T : p18)

In reading the conversation between the Woman of the Lake and Mr. Agwo, one can tell that unlike Flora Nwapa's deity who selects her devotees without consulting, Njideka's consults her prospective disciple before being selected. In fact, in mentioning her worshipper's name to Mr. Agwo and stating what she has to do, one notices that the deity had a talk with Mrs. Egbenuka and told what her duties were all about before she could be her worshipper. After the deity has told Mr. Agwo what to do, the latter acted accordingly in the following way:

So, off he went to Nkwo market where he saw Mrs. Egbenuka. Then he waited by the lake for Mrs. Egbenuka to come, but she did not show up. Mr. Agwo returned to the market and saw Mrs. Egbenuka showing off her wealth to her friends in the market. She did not wear red and white clothing; she was not even prepared to go to Ogbuide Lake. Agwo shook his long neck from left to right as he went down the road to tell Mammywater what he discovered (M.T :20)

Unfortunately for the deity, when Mr. Agwo complied with her instructions, he discovered that Mrs. Egbenuka did not abide by the rules. Instead, Mrs. Egbenuka went to the market to brag about her riches given by the woman of the lake. Following Mrs. Egbenuka's disobedience, the woman of the lake promised to punish her. Njideka's deity did not get discouraged because of the disappointment she faced with Mrs. Egbenuka. As a matter of fact, she contacted another woman called Egondy prior to be her worshipper in the following terms: Mammywater told her that she must wear red and white cloth everyday and she build a shrine in her room with a basin of water and six gold coins in the basin... (M.T : 27 : 28)

Like above, this passage sheds more light on the contrast between Flora Nwapa's woman of the lake and Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka's one. In selecting her disciple, Njideka's deity has to have a conversation with her prospective devotee, through which she tells her worshipper that she would like to choose her as her worshipper and the latter is free to turn down the offer or accept it.

To conclude on the way Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka's woman of the lake selects her disciples, it is germane to argue that contrary to Flora Nwapa's deity who never contacts her prospective devotee prior to the pact, Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka's always has a talk with her future disciple before being her worshipper. After it has been discovered that Flora Nwapa's woman of the lake is different from Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka's when it comes to selecting of devotees, in the following section, the concern is to find out whether each deity clearly states what her disciple will gain in case she obeys the rules, and consequences she faces in case she fails to comply with the rules.

3-THE AFTERMATH OF SIGNING A PACT WITH THE WOMAN OF THE LAKE

Although the title of the section is the aftermath of signing a pact with deity, In this section, the aim is to delve into the books under scrutiny to bring to light whether or not each deity informs her prospective worshipper about the benefit of being her disciple as well as the drawbacks the latter faces in case she fails to abide by the rules. Like above, the section has been divided into two subtitles namely the aftermath of signing a pact with Flora Nwapa's woman of the lake and the aftermath of signing a pact with Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka's woman of the lake.

3.1-The Aftermath of Signing a Pact with Flora Nwapa's Woman of the Lake

As dreaming about the woman of the lake is a proof of having been chosen as a devotee of the deity in Flora Nwapa's fiction, Efur, the main character of Flora Nwapa's first novel under scrutiny, argues what follows while explaining her dreams about the woman of the lake to her father:

"What I have noticed so far each time I dreamt about the woman of the lake was that in the mornings when I went to the market I sold all the things I took to the market. Debtors came of their own accord to pay their debts (1966:146)."

Through this passage, one can tell what a selected disciple of the Lake Goddess can gain in return after having been chosen as the woman of the lake's worshipper. In fact, Uhammiri, that is the deity, provides her devotee with wealth. The fact that Efur sold all her goods and debtors went to pay their debts each time she dreamt about the woman of the lake on eve shows that the deity gives her worshippers wealth. As in any pact there is always a trade off, the sister of Efur's mother-in-law could not help reacting as soon as she heard that Efur had become a mammywater's disciple in the following terms:

"Do I hear that she now has Uhammiri in her bedroom?" Omirima sneered.

"That's what I hear. She and her husband plunged into it. I was not consulted."

"She has spoilt everything. This is bad. How many women in this town who worship Uhammiri have children? Answer me Amede, how many? All right let's count them: Ogini Azogu," she counted off one finger, "she had a son before she became a worshipper of Uhammiri. Since then she has not got another child. Two, Nwanyafor Ojimba, she has no child at all. Three, Uzoechi Negeneg, no child. They are all over the place. Why do we bother ourselves counting them. Your daughter-in-law must be a foolish woman

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to go into that. Amede, you are to blame. Didn't you point this to her? You are the mother, why didn't you point out this to her?... (1966:162)"

In scanning through the extract above, one realizes that once selected as the mammywater's disciple, the person loses fertility in Flora Nwapa's fiction. As a result, the deity's worshipper gets rich on the one hand and loses her fertility on the other hand. Consequently, this swop between the woman of the lake and Efuru is not well appreciated by the members of the society. Igbo people do not like signing a pact with Uhammiri, for them, children are worthier than wealth. Although the person selected by the woman of the lake can later know what she gains and loses from the pact, she does not know the drawbacks she faces whether or not she abides by the deity's rules. This means Flora Nwapa's Uhammiri never tells her devotees anything related to the pact. Thus, Albeit Efuru complied with the woman of the lake's requirements such as putting a shrine in her room and other things, she witnessed a misfortune. As a matter of fact, while Efuru was in Gilbert's house, she fell sick and the diviners consulted could not discover the exact cause of Efuru's sickness. Since Gilbert's mother was tired of contradictory divinations related to the cause of Efuru's illness, a special dibia was recommended to her. When Gilbert's mother went to consult the dibia, the latter stated what follows :

'... the daughter of the great Nwashike Ogene, will not die. She has offended the woman of the lake by neglecting her. So she must appease the woman of the lake with a white hen, that is laying eggs. The eggs of the hen must be thrown into a pot containing palm oil. Unripe plantains, very big ones should be cut into pieces and put in the pot. The pot must be an earthenware pot. The great dibia says that his fee is elevenpence-all in pennies (1966: 215)'

This passage above demonstrates that signing a pact with Flora Nwapa's woman of the lake does not make every clear. In fact, one can never know what might occur once she is the deity's worshipper. The woman of the lake is a jealous deity. Thus, she does not want to share her devotee with anybody. The fact that Efuru serves two masters does not work with the deity. Consequently, she cannot bear the fact that Efuru is on one hand her worshipper and on the other hand married to Gilbert Enerberi. Efuru's sickness is a punishment for cheating on the deity. Although the sacrifice requested by the dibia was performed accordingly, Efuru did not recover. Thus, Omirima, that is Gilbert's aunt posited what follows to Gilbert's mother :

'Amede, your daughter -in-law will die ; She is guilty of adultery. Let her confess and the sickness will leave her. She has wronged the goddess of the land and she is being punished accordingly. She must confess otherwise our ancestors will kill her. I am warning you. It is better for her to confess than to die(1966 : 215-216)'

In reading Amede's words between the lines, she talks about the woman of the lake's jealousy toward her worshipper. In fact, the wrong Efuru is said to have done to the Goddess is her marriage with Gilbert. As a jealous deity, the Lake Goddess does not want either to share or lose Efuru to another person. Thus, the confession Amede mentions that Efuru should do is not to be done in the physical world but in the spiritual one. Efuru's sickness is due to the deity's desire to have the full of control of her devotee. Since the woman of the lake is the Goddess of Igbo people and has power over Igbos, Uhammiri manipulates Efuru who finally divorces her husband as one can tell through the conversation with her friend Difu, the doctor :

...the doctor was silent when Efuru ended her story. Then he asked : 'you will not go back to him ?'

'I thought you were my friend, Difu ? Efuru said horrified.

'I am your friend . I have always been your friend'

'If you are , why then do you want me to go back to the man who accused me of adultery. You don't know the seriousness of the offence(1966 : 2020).'

Efuru's decision to leave Gilbert's house does not depend on herself. In fact, it is the manifestation of the deity's spell in Efuru's life. As the woman of the lake's plan was to have the full control over Efuru, her worshipper, she has spiritually entailed the situation of sickness in Efuru's life which has led her divorcing her husband, Gilbert. Through this passage, Nwapa informs people about the danger of being the deity's worshipper. Although the woman of the lake provides her disciples with wealth, she can spoil her devotees' lives anytime. In other words, whenever one is the woman of the lake's worshipper, she cannot know what lies ahead in her life. As a matter of fact, the Mammywater can destroy her devotee's life whenever she wants. Likewise, having been aware of the danger of being deity's devotee, a Christian musician called Patty Obassey from Igboland, quoted by Obododimma Oha in his article entitled : Flora Nwapa and the Semiotic of the Woman of the Lake, sang a song entitled 'Nwamamaiwota' whose translation in English is 'Mammy water's child' through which she dissuades people from being the woman of the lake's disciples in the following lines :

Mamaiwota bu mmuo ozi a churu n'igwe

O gaa n'osimiri gaa wuo ala eze ya

Kpaba nkata choba onye o ga'elo

I bu ngwa olu mamaiwota ?

Gaa m n'azu nwamamaiwota !

In English :

Mammy water was an angel banished from heaven

She went to the sea and built her kingdom
And started scheming for whom to swallow
Are you Mammy water's instrument ? (F.N : C.P :176)

Through her religious song, Obassey begins by providing people with the background of the woman of the lake's origin and then argues that all that glitters is not gold. That is although Mammywater provides her worshippers with wealth, in fact, it is not genuine riches. Mammywater is a wolf in sheep's clothing, whoever associates with the woman of the lake is doomed to be her prey. As a result signing a pact with the deity is tantamount to signing a pact with death. The woman of the lake kills her devotees whenever she wants. By the same token through a study focused on a comparative appraisal of Elechi Amadi's *The Concubine* and Nwapa's *Efuru* carried out by Eustace Palmer(1972), quoted in *Uhamiry deity and women : A study of Flora Nwapa's Efuru and Idu* by Razinat Mohammed and Abubakar Usman, Palmer posits that the woman of the lake is evil. In fact, because of Efuru's relationship with the woman of the lake, Efuru lives miserable life.

As the woman of the lake's aim is to own Efuru for herself, the fulfilment of her desire came true when, after divorcing Gilbert Eneberi, Efuru had the following dream :

Efuru slept soundly that night. She dreamt of the woman of the lake, her beauty, her long hair and her riches. She had lived for ages at the bottom of the lake. She was as old as the lake itself. She was happy, she was wealthy... (1966 : 221)

The peaceful sleep and the dream about the woman of the lake Efuru had after leaving Gilbert's house show that Efuru's sickness was caused by the deity. Thus, after divorcing her husband, she has recovered and enjoys a peaceful life. The hard times Efuru went through at Gilbert's house were part of the woman of the lake's desire to have her worshipper at her disposal. According to deity, she did not fully own Efuru since she was at the disposal of two spheres : Gilbert in the physical world and the Lake goddess in the supernatural one.

As a conclusion, it is worthy mentioning that in selecting her disciples, Flora Nwapa's deity does not tell her future disciple either what she will gain or undergo in case she disobeys the rules of the pact. Moreover she does not care whether the devotee is obedient or not. As a matter of fact, although Efuru abode by what was stated by the dibia such as performing a sacrifice, putting a shrine in her bedroom and others, Efuru did not enjoy a peaceful life. In fact, the woman of the lake decided to have the full control of Efuru. To fulfil her plan, the woman of the lake entailed a misfortune in Efuru's life by making her seriously sick and divorcing her husband Gilbert to dedicate her total life to the woman of the lake's cult. After investigating the aftermath of signing a pact with Flora Nwapa's woman of the lake, in the following lines, the attention will shift to knowing whether Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka's deity clearly tells her future disciple the profit, and consequences she would face in case she disobeys the rules of the pact.

3.2- The Aftermath of Signing a Pact with Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka's Woman of the Lake.

As a deity has power over her disciples in particular and Igbo people in general, does Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka's Mammywater inform her devotees about the advantages of obeying her and disadvantages of not complying with her rules ? This question is going to be answered through the following part of this section. In fact, once in search of a worshipper, the deity, selected a woman called Egongdu as her worshipper, had a conversation with the latter in the following terms : 'I will give you a child ; it will be a boy. But you must serve me seven days a week. If you do not obey the rules, you will die and so will your son(M.T : 27 : 28).'Through the conversation between Mammywater and her prospective devotee, one can tell that Njideka's deity treats her worshippers fairly. The woman of the lake is not cagey on anything related to the pact. She wants a fair deal. She does not want any members of the pact to be a loser. Consequently, she clearly states the rules of the pact to anybody who is likely to be part of it. Thus, she tells Egongdu that she will get a child if she abides by the rules and will die as well as her son in case she fails to comply with rules.

In short, after the investigation to know whether Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka's deity informs her devotees about the gain, and the consequences of disobeying her rules, it is worthy positing that Njideka's woman of the lake plays it fair with her future disciples. As a matter of fact, before anybody serves her, Mammywater tells the latter on one hand what she will gain in signing a pact, on the other hand what the prospective devotee will face in case she does not respect the rules.

IV-CONCLUSION

As a general conclusion related to the comparison of two women of the lake depicted by two authoresses from Nigeria : Flora Nwapa and Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka, it is germane to argue that investigation has focused on two angles namely first to find out how each deity selects her worshippers and second to discover whether each of the deities informs their prospective devotees about the advantages they gain in signing a pact and the drawbacks they face by not abiding by rules of the pact. Concerning the first angle, it has been concluded that Flora Nwapa's deity does not physically meet with her future devotees prior to their selection but she chooses them while they are unaware of the pact. They only notice their relation with the deity through dreams, the loss of fertility and becoming wealthy. However, contrary to Flora Nwapa's woman of the lake, Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka's comes physically and meet her prospective disciples to select them. As far as the second angle is concerned, Flora Nwapa's mammywater neither tells her future disciples what they will gain nor informs on the consequences she will face once rules are not respected. Unlike Flora Nwapa's woman of the lake, Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka's informs her future disciples about the profit and drawbacks of the pact.

The Contrast Between Flora Nwapa's and Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka's Women of the Lake

Consequently, it is worthy arguing that Flora Nwapa's woman of the lake is evil. As a result, in depicting the woman of the lake in her fiction, the authoress warns people about the danger of signing a pact with a devil. According to Flora Nwapa, people should never trust any deities because they give on the right hand and takes back on the left one. In other words, if a human being signs a pact with a devil, they are doomed to sufferings. However, Njideka Nwapa-Ibuaka's woman of the lake contacts her worshipper physically and tells them what they gain and consequences they face in case they do not respect the rules of their pact.

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